

ENHANCING COMMUNICATION SKILLS THROUGH PRACTICE IN ENGLISH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6555017>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th May 2022

Accepted: 10th May 2022

Online: 15th May 2022

KEY WORDS

communication skills,
practice, development,
speaking skills, language
learners, right practice
approaches, consistency.

ABSTRACT

This article mainly analyzes the ways through which students and learners can improve their communication skills and develop them further. Also, this paper makes some practical researches and emphasizes the importance of regular practice on this matter. The report also claims to give exact information about what is the communication skills. The article is also helpful guide to teachers in increasing students' speaking capabilities. The ideas have been proven with exact views of the authors.

Introduction.

In today's world, communication skills are the most basic skills that every language learner should acquire. Not only this, but also nowadays, we appear to be living in an increasingly communications-driven world, thanks to rapidly changing technology and globalization. "There are few jobs in which individuals may succeed without excellent English communication abilities. So, it clearly shows the importance of having and learning these skills during English language learning journey of one's both in life and in career". [2;75];

However, almost every individual has their own approaches and ways to succeed at it. But for me, as I observed and did some research on this matter, I would say that PRACTICE is the key thing for better communication skills. Regular

practice can highly and effectively help learners both with knowledge and psychology of communication skills. Thus, in this research work, I will describe the so-called "Right practice approaches".

Main part.

English is a lingua franca, meaning it is a "bridge" language: When two people who speak different non-English languages meet, very often the common language they use to connect is English. This is why English is taught in many schools around the globe and why many international corporations are officially mandating English communication for employees in all global locations. [Edunun, 2020]; Approximately 2 billion people speak English now. [Wikipedia, 2022]; English is the third most spoken language in the world, yet it is the first language mastered by non-native speakers. In fact, English is

used as a second language by more individuals than their first language. Having the ability to use English language skills successfully is a major advantage, especially in the job, whether you started learning English communication as a child or much later.

Strong communication skills not only do include speaking, but also other things that we barely pay attention. I'd say that communication skills can be verbal and non-verbal, while they can be in spoken and written forms. When we text others, it's actually written form of communication, and the second spoken form is perhaps the most popular one as everyone knows about it. Also, as I pointed out above communication skills are verbal and non-verbal. In verbal one, we speak and convey certain information to other individuals and in this case, our non-verbal skills also play a significant role. To illustrate this, when we speak, we mostly use our body language with facial gestures and body movement, which also have the ability to convey a message to the listener. But now I want to concentrate on how to develop through practice and what things should students take into consideration while they aim to boost their communication skills by practicing:

- **Consistency**

Being consistent and doing practice on a regular basis for even a short amount of time is a key for one's success;

- **Keeping An Open Mind**

To improve our communication skills which will help with our speaking skills later learners should try to be more approachable and be friendly with others. That's the starting point of every conversation. Having open mind will surely

help to communicate with more people which boosts confidence in speaking;

- **Listening**

Listening to various music, podcasts, audiobooks will assist learners to learn new stuff such as new ideas, the ways certain words are pronounced. As well, it's a great way of practice which is effortless, through it they will develop their ability to speak automatically. Next, by doing this, they learn to understand what their partners are saying and they perhaps become good listeners;

- **Reading**

Reading a lot provides every learner with new ideas, with which students can use during their communication and enhance their vocabulary skills;

It is likely that these strategies may seem quite simple, but indeed, they are quite simple and suitable for every learner. These are the ways through which successful learners completed their English journeys. Additionally, these strategies are very special as they stand out among other strategies for being universal. It is also essential to mention that these strategies can be effectively used by any level learner. What I mean by this, students from elementary level to advanced levels can use them easily and effectively in their language journey.

Conclusion. As before mentioned there's an enormous role of communication skills to show students and improve their speaking. Developing communication skills will have far reaching positive outcomes for the language learners to build excellent speaking skills and can pave way for effective communication by practicing with the right approaches as mentioned above. Moreover, these given popular practice methods can

be used by any teacher in the class as well language learners can do them independently. In one word, the cycle of excellent speaking skills and

communication skills begins with the right practice techniques.

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